

Trade study of dc-dc converter topologies for non-propulsive energy generation from aircraft propulsive electrical networks

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Abstract— The development of effective power electronics systems has received a lot of attention in recent aerospace research, which has focused on the advancement of all-electric aircraft. Delivering revolutionary technologies to electrical distribution for upcoming hybrid-electric aircraft is the goal of the HECATE (Hybrid-Electric regional Aircraft distribution TEchnologies) project. HECATE. This article focuses making a thorough trade analysis of DC/DC converter topologies designed for hybrid-electric and all-electric aircraft applications. Where the trade study will focus on 800 V, 150 kW DC/DC converter while taking aviation standards compliance, power density and efficiency.

Keywords— DAB, Electrified propulsion, LLC, All-electric aircraft, DC/DC converters.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global aviation sector is facing increasing environmental and market pressure, urging the aviation industry to search for more environmentally friendly solutions. Thus to become more environmentally friendly both research and industry have been focused on how to electrify aircrafts and what challenges can arise from [1]-[3]. Even Airbus has launched multiple programs to ensure that the transformation to more electric and all electric aircraft can be met [4]. This article mainly focuses on the target from FlightPath 2050, assigned by the advisory council for aeronautics research in Europe (ACARE), electrical aircraft and new power electronics are needed. FlightPath 2050 requires to have a net-zero CO₂ emissions for all intra-EU flights and those departing the EU and to reduce the production of NO_x emissions by 90% of those departing the EU by the year 2050. Also to meet the market forecast that have been presented by Airbus where it is expected that by 2040 there will be a demand of more than 39,000 aircrafts of which 15,000 are replacement of older and less fuel-efficient models [5].

Collins Aerospace aims to lead electrified solutions for power systems on airborne platforms to reduce emissions and to improve efficiency and reliability. Collins Aerospace is the coordinator of the HECATE program [6], a Clean Aviation program focused on defining and designing the electrical architecture of next generation electrical aircraft. This initiative has a funding of 40 M€ with 37 partners. HECATE is also focused on developing technology bricks for More Electric Aircraft (MEA) and All Electric Aircrafts (AEA) paving the way for sustainable and innovative flight solutions.

This work discusses a trade study of used comparing state-of-the-art converters in the range of hundreds of kW and with an input voltage between 700 and 900 V. The article discusses different isolated converters where the primary goal of this study is to conduct a trade-off analysis, evaluating each topology in terms of performance, efficiency, design challenges, and overall suitability for aircraft applications. From this study, the output of this article can identify the most appropriate choice for all-electric aircraft and provide practical recommendations for future developments.

The sections in this article are divided as follows; Section II describes the architecture of the aircraft and where this converter shall be implemented. Section III discusses the state of the art of converters. Section IV discusses the trade-off studies Section V provides a discussion related to the trade-off activities and closing remarks.

II. HECATE – ELECTRICAL ARCHITECTURE

The HECATE electrical architecture provides the next evolution for aircraft electrification considering not only more electrical aircraft loads but the interfacing with electrical propulsion. The architecture can be divided into three sub-systems: primary distribution for propulsive loads, primary distribution for non-propulsive loads and secondary distribution, see Fig. 1. This electrical architecture has been

defined with four different voltage levels in mind: KHVDC, HVDC, LVDC and LVAC.

- LVDC (red) and LVAC (blue) at 28 V and 115 Vac, respectively, provide power to legacy loads similarly to current flying aircrafts such as the ATR72. Typically, this refers to avionics and communication systems, lighting, etc. This network is also referred as the secondary distribution.
- HVDC (green) which could be 270 V or +/- 270 V provides power to bigger energy consumer in alignment with more electrical aircraft approaches, such as, environmental control systems, ice protection systems, etc. An example for this network can be found in current more electrical aircraft such as Boeing 787 [6].
- KHVDC (purple) at 800 V nominal voltage is used to provide power to both the propulsive and the non-propulsive networks. Therefore, the KHVDC

network supplies the motor control unit responsible for power the electrical machine providing support to the thermal engine in a hybrid electrical aircraft. This is a novel electrical network that will require safety and performance evaluation.

The architecture shown in Fig. 1 is powered through a battery, fuel cell or combination of both, which is then connected to a dc-dc converter responsible for generating the KHVDC bus. Another dc-dc converter which is highlighted in red in Fig. 1 is responsible for converting KHVDC to HVDC in order to generate the primary non-propulsive distribution. This converter will be the focus of the trade-off study performed in this work aiming to provide answers on the most promising topologies to use in future electrical aircraft.

From the HVDC bus, two converters are connected to generate the LVDC and LVAC voltage that are used to supply most aircraft legacy loads.

Fig. 1: HECATE EPGDS architecture with the KHVDC-HVDC dc-dc power converter highlighted in red.

III. STATE OF THE ART REVIEW

During the review of the available literature numerous candidates were identified. Consequently, a nomenclature is proposed to help the reader. Fig. 2 presents a general topology structure formed by three main building blocks: inverter, magnetic/resonant tank and rectifier. The nomenclature from now on used is based on this structure and aims to help on the identification and the classification of the main cases considered.

Following this, each topology is identified as follows: “Number of Levels and inverter topology”- “Magnetic tank and transformer configuration” – “Number of levels and rectifier topology”, see for the full glossary. As a matter of example, a three-level half bridge inverter with an LLC centered-tap transformer magnetic tank and a two-level synchronous rectifier is labelled as “3LHB-LLC2T-2LSR”. Based on previous literature, the most suitable isolated topologies identified belong to two families of dc-dc converters: Dual-Active-Bridge (DAB) and resonant

converters. Both families are reported in literature as highly efficient and compact.

Resonant converter main limitations are their light load performance and the complexity to achieve zero-current switching (ZCS) at the synchronous rectifier. DAB offers seamless bidirectional operation. However, its performance gets penalized at light loads and voltage gain may not be close to unity.

The selected resonant dc-dc converters are listed as follow:

- 2LHB-LLC2T-2LSR is the most common LLC configuration and the main research effort around this topology is mainly focused on the gating of the synchronous rectifier to achieve ZCS [8].
- 2LHB-LLC-2LFB could improve the thermal load distribution of the 2LFB compared with the 2LSR. An improved conduction angle analysis of the 2LFB rectifier is provided in [9].
- 2LFB-CLLC-2LFB is presented in [10] as a bidirectional compatible solution. Conventional LLC based resonant converters experience limitations when bidirectional operation is required because of the asymmetric resonant tank gain.
- 2L3PH-LLC3PH-2LFB is introduced in [11] as an alternative to interleaved tank structure to split the current on the resonant tank. This is important to target smaller resonant elements. Additionally, the 3PH primary configuration provides lower conduction losses.
- Candidates 3LHB-LLC2T-2LSR [12], 3LHB-LLC-2LSR [13] and 3LHB-LLC-2LFB [14,15] are a more suitable solutions with higher voltage and higher gains compared with the previous 2L cases. Nonetheless, it is reasonable to expect higher conduction losses. Furthermore, special modulation strategy to optimize the converter performance are required, some reported in [13] and [14,15].
- 2LHB-LCLC2T-2LSR with an LCLC resonant instead of an LLC is here evaluated as an option capable of achieving higher efficiency [16]. However, it is considered that the extra capacitor might hinder reliability.

Similarly, eight DAB converter topologies have been selected, and are listed as follow:

- 2LFB-DAB-2LFB can be considered as the traditional DAB topology [17], which is widely used under single phase-shift control with a wide zero-voltage switching (ZVS) operation range with gains close to unit.
- 2LSHB-DAB-2LSHB is proposed in the literature to reduce the number of switches [18]. However, this requires split dc-link capacitors with neutral point access to ensure symmetry on the transformer's voltages.
- 2LFB-DAB2P-2LFB is a two-port version of the traditional full-bridge DAB is introduced in [19]. This is considered a relevant option for multi-output applications, despite it is worth to note that dedicated control for cross-regulation among ports might be needed.

To extend the voltage range the traditional DAB can be applied to multi-level-based DAB, such as:

- 3LNPFB-DAB-2LFB can provide high static gain, where only one of the bridges needs add extra switches to withstand high voltage [20].

- 3LNPHB-DAB-2LFB, where in this case a half-bridge is utilized instead. Note that symmetry on the dc-link caps is naturally a requirement [21].

- 3LNPFB-DAB-3LNPFB can be considered a complete three-level version of the traditional DAB. This topology is view as relevant to high voltage applications, where conduction losses have lower impact than switching losses. Nevertheless, it has a high switches count [22].

Finally, three-phases DAB versions are included in the review because of their lower current level conducted per phase which can be of interest due to the high currents on the output of the converter. The three-phase topologies studied are:

- 2L3PHDABYY-2L3PH provides more degrees of freedom on the control variables at the cost of even further complexity [23].
- 3LNP3PH-DABYY-3LNP3PH combines the three-phases advantage with a more suitable solution to higher voltages [24].

Table 1 – Nomenclature glossary.

Code	Description
Common to Inverter/Rectifier topology	
NP	Neutral Clamped Point
3PH	Three-phases
HB	Half Bridge
FB	Full Bridge
Magnetic / Tank transformer configuration	
2T	Center-tap primary winding
2P	Two parallel secondary windings
3PHY	Three-phase star-star
3PHYD	Three-phase star-delta
3PHDY	Three-phase delta-star
3PHDD	Three-phase delta-delta
Exclusive to Rectifier topology	
SHB	Symmetrical Half-Bridge
SR	Synchronous Rectifier

Fig. 2: General topology structure and nomenclature

IV. TRADE-OFF ANALYSIS

Finding the best candidate for the application here evaluated is not a straightforward decision. To narrow down the listed candidates in previous section and finally identified the suitable candidate to be evaluated as the final solution for the technology gap here detected, the trade-off methodology displayed in Fig. 3 is proposed.

The methodology is based on three evaluation phases: “Topology Pre-selection”, “Loss Model Refinement” and “Preliminary Design Assessment”. Please note each phase aims to discard the Best promising cases while increasing the detail and complexity of the analysis. In the following lines the steps followed in each of the phases and the results obtained for the current study case are explained.

Fig. 3: Trade-off methodology flow-chart.

A. Phase 1: Topology Pre-Selection

The selection of state-of-the-art topologies has been evaluated from a theoretical point of view. The following characteristics have been analyzed from a qualitative perspective: efficiency, control and design complexity, weight, and switch devices necessary blocking voltage. Discrete color labels have been assigned to each evaluation criteria, with a comparative linear distribution among the topologies. The resulting analysis is presented in Table 2.

From Table 2 several topologies are already a clear no-go for the application, such as the 3LNP3PH-DABYY-3LNP3PH, for instance. For topologies with minimal structural variation among them, the highest overall score is preferred. Other topologies such as the 2LSHB-DAB-2LSHB, although the scoring high on most of the items, have practical drawbacks for the power level as the increased number of capacitors. Overall, the pre-selection of topologies follows the performance indicators in Table 2 as well as Collins Aerospace best practices.

Table 2 - Results for theoretical state of the art analysis

Topology	Efficiency	Complexity		Weight	Blocking Voltage
		Control	Design		
3LHB-LLC2T-2LSR	●	●	●	●	●
2LFB-LLC2T-SR	●	●	●	●	●
2LHB-LCLC-2LSR	●	●	●	●	●
3LHB-LLC-FR	●	●	●	●	●
2LHB-LLC-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
2LFB-LLC-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
2LFB-CLLC-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
2LHB-LLC-2LSR	●	●	●	●	●
3LHB-LLC-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
3LFB-LLC-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
3LDB-LLC2T-2LSR	●	●	●	●	●
2L3PH-LLC3PH-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
2LFB-DAB-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
2LSHB-DAB-2LSHB	●	●	●	●	●
3LNPFb-DAB-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
3LNPHB-DAB-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
3LNPFb-DAB-3LNPFb	●	●	●	●	●
2LFB-DAB2P-2LFB	●	●	●	●	●
2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH	●	●	●	●	●
3LNP3PH-DABYY-3LNP3PH	●	●	●	●	●

B. Phase 2: Loss Model Refinement

The previous list of candidate topologies in Table 2 has been narrowed down to 7 converters: 2LFB-LLC2T-SR, 2LFB-LLC-2LFB, 3LHB-LLC-2LFB, 3LFB-LLC-2LFB, 2LFB-DAB-2LFB, 3LNPFb-DAB-2LFB and 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH.

At this phase of the trade analysis, the objective is to remove the bias different applications in the literature could cause to the metrics in efficiency for each of the 7 topologies. In that regard, a Simulink model based on Simscape toolbox is created for each candidate topology. To keep a fair comparison among topologies, one power module part number is selected per breakdown voltage (e.g., 1200V, 1700V, etc.) and used to model the Simscape MOSFET block.

From the results obtained at this phase, it is clear that 2LFB-LLC2T-SR, 3LHB-LLC-2LFB, 3LFB-LLC-2LFB and 3LNPFb-DAB-2LFB are not suitable for the goal application. For the 3L topologies, the benefits of multilevel structures are not a decisive factor for the 800V input voltage, while the addition of series switches hinders the conduction losses. For the center-tapped LLC, the losses issue is transferred to the secondary side switches, where a full-bridge structure is preferred to mitigate the problem.

C. Phase 3: Preliminary Design Assessment

As the number of candidate topologies narrows down once again, the complexity of the analysis increases. During phase 3, the total number of topologies was reduced to three, being them: 2LFB-LLC-2LFB, 2LFB-DAB-2LFB and 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH. The selected topologies are now designed and assessed in a preliminary stage close to prototyping. To standardize and keep a fair assessment, this phase utilizes the same set of requirements and part numbers (PNs) to design each topology. For the 2LFB-LLC-2LFB, the design procedure followed is based on [24] while the 2LFB-DAB-2LFB and 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH follow the analysis presented in [26] and [27], respectively.

The selection of a limited set of off-the-shelf part numbers yields a straightforward cost and geometrical assessment of the preliminary design, while the losses model can be refined from phase 2 with further details.

The results are then compared under four key parameter indicators (KPI): Efficiency, weight, volume and cost. Each KPI is then converter into a cost function varying from 0 to 1, with limits established from the ideal case to the minimum acceptable under the application requirements. Fig. 4 shows the graphical examples of the cost functions [28].

Fig. 4: Example of cost functions for the trade-off KPIs.

The final figure of merit (FoM) to compare the topologies is formed as a weighted sum of the cost functions:

$$FoM = k_e \cdot CF_e + k_c \cdot CF_c + k_w \cdot CF_w + k_v \cdot CF_v$$

where: k_e , k_c , k_w and k_v are the FoM weights for efficiency, cost, weight, and volume and defined as $k_e + k_c + k_w + k_v = 1$; and CF_e , CF_c , CF_w and CF_v are the cost function values for efficiency, cost, weight, and volume, respectively.

The final FoM yields an objective way to compare topologies regarding the most important KPIs and their priorities reflected by the FoM weights. In

Fig. 5 the outcome of the trade-off analysis is summarized. As can be seen, the 2LFB-LLC-2LFB and 2LFB-DAB-2LFB come very close on their final FoM score, being the DAB the appointed best solution according to the metrics employed. Although the LLC may present better

efficiency, the presence of the resonant capacitor at this particular power level hinders the LLC scores in weight, volume and cost, thus explaining the DAB best overall FoM.

Fig. 5: FoM results on trade-off phase 3.

V. DISCUSSION

This article presents a trade study for an isolated dc/dc converters for a MEA and AEA application. The analysis in the paper simplifies the isolated converter into three main blocks, as shown in Fig. 2: a) inverter, b) magnetic & tank, and c) rectifier. The trade-off study, throughout its different phases, examined various aspects of the converter that included efficiency, soft-switching, control and design complexity, volume, and weight.

From the literature survey, containing tens of candidate topologies, to the final phase of the trade-off, where the three main candidate topologies were preliminarily designed and compared, a clear methodology was established and discussed in the paper. The philosophy behind the trade-off methodology is presented in Fig. 3, where analysis complexity is compromised against higher volume of topologies.

The conclusion of the study is then presented in

Fig. 5. As briefly discussed before, the 2LFB-LLC-2LFB and 2LFB-DAB-2LFB have a close FoM final score, being the DAB the appointed best solution for the application and the 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH the least attractive option.

Analysing the lower score of the 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH, the reason can be traced to a compromise between cost and efficiency. Compared to the other two topologies, the three-phase DAB has four extra switches, meaning two extra half-bridge power modules. During the phase 3 of trade-off, when fixing the power modules part number to be equal among the topologies, the price of such high power PN's will significantly hinder the 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH cost KPI, while mildly improving the efficiency KPI. On the other hand, the granularity of PN's available at this power level is low, thus even if allowing the 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH to be deployed with lower current-rated power modules, the improvement on cost is minor and the efficiency now is lowered. On top of that, the three-phase transformer required for the topology also will imply in an inherently more expensive component, once again lowering the topology FoM score. Other aspects as modulation complexity, although not traded during phase 3, can also negatively impact the 2L3PH-DABYY-2L3PH selection.

On a more detailed view of the two remaining topologies in Fig. 5 results, the nearly identical scores between 2LFB-LLC-2LFB and 2LFB-DAB-2LFB can be directly correlated to their similar structures. Using the block approach introduced by Fig. 2, both topologies share the same Inverter and Rectifier blocks, with the only difference being at the Magnetic & Tank block where the LLC has an extra component (i.e., resonant capacitor).

Under the evaluated KPIs forming the FoM, the identical blocks have the same impact on Cost, Weight and Volume, and the difference between topologies will negatively pend toward the LLC, where the extra capacitor adds penalty to the three aforementioned KPIs. Moreover, at the intended application power level, the resonant capacitor in the LLC is not a trivial component, and its impact on the KPIs cannot completely reflect practical challenges.

On the other hand, it is the efficiency that levels out the LLC with the DAB FoM score. When it comes to soft-switching capability, both topologies are able to ZVS their 8 switches at nominal load, if designed adequately. The LLC presents further advantages on also being able to ZCS the secondary full-bridge, once again subjective to design point and operation point. This entails part of the LLC higher scores on efficiency, but not the totality of it. The other share comes from the differences on conduction losses between topologies. While the DAB needs to reach a compromising between lower recirculating current and extended ZVS range, the LLC at its resonant point has a theoretical purely sinusoidal current circulating through its magnetic and tank. Hence, under such conditions, the currents circulating in the DAB will present a higher RMS value to the same power transfer.

Beyond the trade-off discussed in section IV, several practical challenges related to both topologies need to be analyzed and factored in the final selection. From a manufacturing point of view, the implementation risks in the LLC can be listed as:

- Integrating the resonant inductor in the transformer can prove to be challenging. Besides the difficulties of leakage control at high power transformers, the necessity of a precise ratio between magnetizing and resonant inductance in the LLC can lead to a complex balance between parameters precision and losses.
- Upon the inability to reach target leakage inductance in the transformer, the design options for the LLC are limited to: 1) External inductor addition: if the achievable leakage is lower than the target, an extra external inductor can be added to complement. This results in extra weight and lower integration. 2) Design point change: with the achieved leakage and magnetizing, the design point can be adapted by changing the resonant capacitance value. Although feasible, this option yield a suboptimal converter design.
- Similarly to the power modules, for the rated power level the granularity of available magnetic cores PN is low, therefore limiting the optimization universe available for the transformer design. This can also lead to significant challenges between meeting weight and volume targets while being able to cool the transformer down.
- Due to the specifics of the application and mainly the high power level, the series resonant capacitor will very unlikely be off-the-shelf, but rather custom made. The

component composition presents a combination of challenges regarding thermal management, isolation, and capacitance value. Thermal and isolation are simply tackled by the addition of parallel and series elements, respectively. However, it is the necessity of a precise capacitance value (in contrast to dc-link capacitances, for instance) which hinders the component volume and weight. Other practical aspects such as terminals' skin effect, current sharing and failure mode are added risks to the component.

Similar to the LLC, most of the risks related to the DAB involve the transformer. However, the relaxed requirements in terms of magnetizing inductance and the absence of the series resonant capacitance, simplifies the mitigation of such risk in the DAB. In specific, the DAB risks can be listed as:

- As in the LLC, integration of the series inductance of the DAB into the transformer is key for high power density. Leakage control can be complex in high power transformers, and if incapable of reaching the inductance target, the solutions are once again limited to addition of external inductance or modification of the converter's operating point, with their respective drawbacks previously discussed.
- The compromise between recirculating current (conduction losses) and ZVS range (switching losses) in the DAB can be highly impacted by the series inductance. Upon the inductance integration to the transformer, parametric variations may cause the converter to operate out of its optimal point.

In both topologies, the transformer design is proven to be the most decisive element. Its operation in terms of thermal management, integration and geometric requirements is paramount to the success of the application, while keeping precision in key parameters for the topologies' operation. Although, both LLC and DAB require the series inductance integration in the transformer, the LLC brings extra complexity on its sensitivity to the magnetizing/leakage ratio for the converter operation. Together with the series resonant capacitance practical challenges. Although close scores in the FoM presented in Fig. 5, practical challenges on the LLC such as the series capacitance realization and the more complicated transformer design clearly set the differences between the two topologies, therefore indicating the DAB as the best suited for the application.

In conclusion, technology progression around magnetic components and capacitors has made the LLC a true contender against the DAB in a power and current range in which the DAB was the preferred solution. However, as it stands, the DAB due to the maturity of technology and its advantages in terms of EMI filter design, which is not covered under this work, due to not having a variable frequency range can be considered a better solution for aerospace applications. Further technology developments can push the LLC or its DCX variants as a feasible solution for high power applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Barzkar and M. Ghassemi, "Electric Power Systems in More and All Electric Aircraft: A Review," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 169314-169332, 2020P. J. Ansell, "Hydrogen-Electric Aircraft Technologies and Integration: Enabling an environmentally sustainable aviation future," in *IEEE Electrification Magazine*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 6-16, June 2022.
- [2] "Royce advances hybrid-electric flight with new technology to lead the way in Advanced air mobility," Rolls, <https://www.rolls-royce.com/media/press-releases/2022/22-06-2022-rr-advances-hybrid-electric-flight-with-new-technology.aspx> (accessed Feb. 18, 2025).
- [3] A. Elwakeel, E. Ertekin, M. Elshiekh, M. Iftikhar, W. Yuan and M. Zhang, "Protection System Architecture for All-Electric Aircraft," in *IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 1-7, Aug. 2023, Art no. 5203707, doi: 10.1109/TASC.2023.3248529.
- [4] "Airbus UpNext," Airbus, <https://www.airbus.com/en/innovation/innovation-ecosystem/airbus-upnext> (accessed Feb. 18, 2025). P. Wheeler, T. S. Sirimanna, S. Bozhko and K. S. Haran, "Electric/Hybrid-Electric Aircraft Propulsion Systems," in *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 109, no. 6, pp. 1115-1127, June 2021
- [5] "2024 global market forecast," Airbus, <https://www.airbus.com/en/products-services/commercial-aircraft/global-market-forecast> (accessed Feb. 19, 2025).
- [6] "Consortium," Hecate, <https://hecate-project.eu/consortium/> (accessed Feb. 18, 2025).
- [7] Boeing, "787 Electrical System" [Online] Available: <http://787updates.newairplane.com/787-Electrical-Systems/787-Electrical-System>
- [8] C. Sun, Q. Sun, R. Wang, P. Zhang, L. Zhang and P. Wang, "Universal Synchronous Rectification Scheme for LLC Resonant Converter Using Primary-Side Inductor Voltage," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 70, no. 6, pp. 5747-5759, June 2023, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2022.3199946
- [9] M. Mohammadi and M. Ordenez, "Synchronous Rectification of LLC Resonant Converters Using Homopolarity Cycle Modulation," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 1781-1790, March 2019, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2018.2840493.
- [10] N. Chen *et al.*, "Synchronous Rectification Based on Resonant Inductor Voltage for CLLC Bidirectional Converter," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 547-561, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2021.3100154
- [11] Salem, Mohamed & Ramachandaramurthy, Vigna K. & Jusoh, Awang & Padmanaban, Sanjeevikumar & Kamarol, Mohamad & Teh, Jiashen & Ishak, Dahaman. (2020). Three-Phase Series Resonant DC-DC Boost Converter with Double LLC Resonant Tanks and Variable Frequency Control. *IEEE Access*. 8. 22386 - 22399. 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2969546.
- [12] I. -O. Lee and G. -W. Moon, "Analysis and Design of a Three-Level LLC Series Resonant Converter for High- and Wide-Input-Voltage Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 2966-2979, June 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2011.2174381.
- [13] F. Wu, Z. Wang and S. Luo, "Buck-Boost Three-Level Semi-Dual-Bridge Resonant Isolated DC-DC Converter," in *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 5986-5995, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JESTPE.2020.3041094.
- [14] C. Lu, W. Hu and F. C. Lee, "Neutral-Point Voltage Balancing Methods of Series-Half-Bridge LLC Converter for Solid State Transformer," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 7060-7073, June 2021, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2020.3035150
- [15] A. Coccia, F. Canales, P. Barbosa and S. Ponnaluri, "Wide input voltage range compensation in DC/DC resonant architectures for on-board traction power supplies," 2007 European Conference on Power Electronics and Applications, Aalborg, Denmark, 2007, pp. 1-10, doi: 10.1109/EPE.2007.4417709

- [16] R. -L. Lin and Lung-Hua Huang, "Efficiency improvement on LLC resonant converter using integrated LCLC resonant transformer," *2016 IEEE Industry Applications Society Annual Meeting*, Portland, OR, USA, 2016, pp. 1-8, doi: 10.1109/IAS.2016.7731862
- [17] Salem, Mohamed & Ramachandaramurthy, Vigna K. & Jusoh, Awang & Padmanaban, Sanjeevikumar & Kamarol, Mohamad & Teh, Jiashen & Ishak, Dahaman. (2020). Three-Phase Series Resonant DC-DC Boost Converter with Double LLC Resonant Tanks and Variable Frequency Control. *IEEE Access*. 8. 22386 - 22399. 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2969546
- [18] N. M. L. Tan, T. Abe and H. Akagi, "Design and Performance of a Bidirectional Isolated DC–DC Converter for a Battery Energy Storage System," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 1237-1248, March 2012, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2011.2108317.
- [19] P. Liu, C. Chen, S. Duan and W. Zhu, "Dual Phase-Shifted Modulation Strategy for the Three-Level Dual Active Bridge DC–DC Converter," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 10, pp. 7819-7830, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2017.2696488.
- [20] R. M. Burkart and J. W. Kolar, "Comparative η – ρ – σ Pareto Optimization of Si and SiC Multilevel Dual-Active-Bridge Topologies With Wide Input Voltage Range," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 5258-5270, July 2017, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2016.2614139
- [21] R. M. Burkart and J. W. Kolar, "Comparative η – ρ – σ Pareto Optimization of Si and SiC Multilevel Dual-Active-Bridge Topologies With Wide Input Voltage Range," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 32, no. 7, pp. 5258-5270, July 2017, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2016.2614139.
- [22] P. Liu, C. Chen, S. Duan and W. Zhu, "Dual Phase-Shifted Modulation Strategy for the Three-Level Dual Active Bridge DC–DC Converter," in *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 64, no. 10, pp. 7819-7830, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.1109/TIE.2017.2696488.
- [23] H. van Hoek, M. Neubert and R. W. De Doncker, "Enhanced Modulation Strategy for a Three-Phase Dual Active Bridge—Boosting Efficiency of an Electric Vehicle Converter," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 28, no. 12, pp. 5499-5507, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2013.2251905.
- [24] N. H. Baars, C. G. E. Wijnands and J. Everts, "A Three-Level Three-Phase Dual Active Bridge DC-DC Converter with a Star-Delta Connected Transformer," *2016 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC)*, Hangzhou, China, 2016, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/VPPC.2016.7791601
- [25] S. De Simone, AN2450 application note, url: <https://www.semice.com/file/backup/STMICROELECTRONICS-AN2450.pdf> (accessed Sep. 21, 2023).
- [26] S. Shao, M. Jiang, W. Ye, Y. Li, J. Zhang and K. Sheng, "Optimal Phase-Shift Control to Minimize Reactive Power for a Dual Active Bridge DC–DC Converter," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 10193-10205, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2018.2890292
- [27] N. H. Baars, J. Everts, H. Huisman, J. L. Duarte and E. A. Lomonova, "A 80-kW Isolated DC–DC Converter for Railway Applications," in *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 30, no. 12, pp. 6639-6647, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TPEL.2015.2396006
- [28] Shephard, Ronald William. *Theory of Cost and Production Functions*. Germany: Princeton University Press, 2015.